

Increasing FAIRness of data processing in Occupational Health and Safety (OHS)

Version 0

Funder

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Grant

Implementing FAIR Principles in the Field of Occupational Safety and Health (OSH)

Researchers

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Organizations

Riga Stradiņš University

Datasets

Title: [The work conditions and risks in Latvia national surveys](#)

Template: [RSU DMP Template](#)

The Work conditions and risks in Latvia national surveys were conducted in Latvia in 2006, 2010, 2013, 2018 and 2021. The aim of these surveys is to gather evidence on situations related to occupational risk factors, occupational health, safety and to analyze the dynamics of the data obtained and identify the causes of the existing problems. This data serves as a basis to develop proposals for improving the practical implementation of the legal framework and foundation for effective decision making.

Study "Working conditions and risks in Latvia" surveys of employees, employers, Latvian residents aged 15-74 (except for the 2nd study), occupational health and safety specialists (except for the 3rd study) and patients with registered occupational diseases (except for the 2nd and 3rd study) have been conducted periodically five times since 2006.

The Work conditions and risks in Latvia national surveys data are collected for the research purpose and it relates to the project aim to implement FAIR principles in practice by transforming collected research data in the field of Occupational safety and health (OSH), and to create an openly accessible research data platform.

Dataset Description

1.1 Purpose of data

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The Work conditions and risks in Latvia national surveys were conducted in Latvia in 2006, 2010, 2013, 2018 and 2021. The aim of these surveys is to gather evidence on situations related to occupational risk factors, occupational health, safety and to analyse the dynamics of the data obtained and identify the causes of the existing problems. This data serves as a basis to develop

proposals for improving the practical implementation of the legal framework and foundation for effective decision making.

Study "Working conditions and risks in Latvia" surveys of employees, employers, Latvian residents aged 15-74 (except for the 2nd study), occupational health and safety specialists (except for the 3rd study) and patients with registered occupational diseases (except for the 2nd and 3rd study) have been conducted periodically five times since 2006.

The Work conditions and risks in Latvia national surveys data are collected for the research purpose and it relates to the project aim to implement FAIR principles in practice by transforming collected research data in the field of Occupational safety and health (OSH), and to create an openly accessible research data platform.

1.1.2 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")?

Data could be useful to several groups: researchers in occupational health field, students of the university, occupational safety practitioners, governmental institutions (for example State labor inspectorate), non-governmental organisations (for example Employer's confederation of Latvia).

1.2 Data characteristics

1.2.1 Type of data generated/collected

Survey data

1.2.2 Format of data generated/collected

- csv
- sav

1.2.3 Expected volume of the data

- a. 4647 KB
- b. 6398 KB
- c. 2152 KB

d. 5692 KB

e. 4324 KB

1.2.4 Are you re-using this dataset?

No

The datasets haven't been published yet, therefore we can't give any reference to previous datasets, however this project is exactly meaning to make these datasets reusable in future.

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers - DOI)?

Yes

doi

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

DDI (Data Documentation Initiative)

We may add additional metadata regarding specifics of the field

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.1.6 Will you document the dataset?

Yes

- codebook
- readme file
- questionnaire

- methodology description

2.2 Data accessibility

2.2.1 Are the data formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

Data will be stored in CSV format which is widely available for most of applications dealing with tabular data. We also plan to store SAV file, therefore making it accessible in SPSS software.

2.2.2 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Data will be accessible with most of the software tools, including MS Excel, SPSS, coding platforms (such as Python, R) and others.

2.2.3 Is it possible to include the relevant software in the dataset (e.g. source code)?

No

2.2.4 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy/ontology to make your data interoperable?

No

Data mostly consist of survey questions and answers to them which will be described in the following documents to make them understandable for other researchers. If possible, until the end of project we will consult with ESENER who have long experience in aligning data from different countries.

2.3 Data publishing and long-term preservation

2.3.2 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?
Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

Data is made by efforts of researchers at RSU Institute of Occupational Safety and Environmental Health, therefore it would be appreciated that dataset is cited also in other studies.

2.3.3 What type of access the dataset will have (choose one)?

restricted, request access (access is restricted, but request with collaboration proposal could be submitted to the authors)

Dataset will be shared upon request to other researchers or students who are aiming to use it for research purposes. Dataset may be shared also to state institutions for policy planning or monitoring purposes.

2.3.4 Will there be an embargo period for access to these data?

Yes

2024-07-31

Embargo period will be applied to last survey period (2021) dataset in all study samples until July 2024 in order to publish scientific results.

2.3.5 When data will be made available for re-use?

2023-07-31

Data will be available for re-use for at least 10 years (further researchers will assess necessity for longer preservation). Dataset is important, because it covers longitudinal study which could be compared also to similar future studies.

2.3.6 Will you provide reference to the dataset in scientific publications and other research outputs?

Yes

2.3.7 Other relevant remarks

We will provide reference to the dataset in scientific publications and other research outputs. Data users should refer to the dataset in case of data use. In historical scientific publications we will contact the publishers about the possibilities to provide references.

3.1 Allocation of resources and quality assurance

3.1.1 Which costs will be covered within this project for making data FAIR?

- archiving
- processing

3.1.2 Have you discussed how the costs will be covered?

All costs for processing and archiving data will be covered by the project "Implementing FAIR Principles in the Field of Occupational Safety and Health (OSH)" (cascading grant under EOSC-Future project funded in Horizon2020 research and innovation framework programme). Only costs for human resources (remuneration) will be covered within this project, because other

(such as licences, workplaces) are covered by the university. Costs for reuse and long-term preservation after the project will be covered by university or other projects.

3.1.3 Which institutions are responsible for handling the data?

Riga Stradiņš University

In this activity only Riga Stradins University will be involved.

3.1.4 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

- Ingmars Kreismanis (orcid: [0000-0002-3408-7365](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3408-7365))
- Svetlana Lakisa (orcid: [0000-0002-8707-1359](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8707-1359))
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- Ivars Vanadzīņš (orcid: [0000-0002-5391-1583](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5391-1583))

Ingmars Kreismanis (RDM manager) will be responsible for overseeing the process (consulted by Ivars Vanadzins (the director of the respective institute)), guidance and alignment with other activities. Data description and processing will be done by Svetlana Lakisa and Linda Paegle (researchers at the institute).

3.1.5 Are there data quality assurance processes foreseen?

Yes

Data will be processed and published according to FAIR principles and best practice guidelines. After the project RSU will ensure periodic quality assessment procedures (in case of necessity, new versions of the datasets will be published). Quality improvements may be made also when the dataset is re-used by third parties, taking into account their recommendations.

Quality assurance will be ensured according to internal policy and procedure which is developed at the moment.

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall
- Passwords

All data during the project is stored on university data storage which is protected by passwords and centralized and local firewalls. Access is given only to responsible employees to the respective files.

3.2.2 What provisions are in place for data security?

- Data access
- Data storage
- Data recovery
- Data sharing

Data is accessible only to relevant parties of the project. Data is stored in a safe infrastructure and protected by passwords and firewalls. Data recovery is possible because backups are made regularly. Data can be shared to other employees.

3.2.3 Where the data will be stored during research?

Data will be stored only in the infrastructure described above during research.

3.2.4 Have you ensured that your chosen repository is appropriate for long term preservation and curation?

Yes

Yes, RSU Dataverse is based on Dataverse code which is applicable for long-term preservation of the data. University will administer and update the repository on regular basis, as well as ensure data curation.

3.3 Ethical and legal aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

Data has been anonymized prior to this project, so there are no ethical or legal issues.

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data (if applicable)?

Yes

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data?

No

3.3.5 Will data collected/generated include sensitive information?

No

3.3.6 If yes, what are the methods used to process and access personal data/sensitive information

anonymising data

Title: [Laboratory-performed occupational risk factors measurements data](#)

Template: [RSU DMP Template](#)

This dataset consists of laboratory-performed occupational risk factors measurements data (such as occupational noise, whole body, and hand-arm vibration, indoor lighting, air temperature, relative humidity, airflow (indoor), chemicals concentration in work environment air, etc.) during the period from 1995 to 2021.

Dataset Description

1.1 Purpose of data

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

This dataset consists of laboratory-performed occupational risk factors measurements data (such as occupational noise, whole body, and hand-arm vibration, indoor lighting, air temperature, relative humidity, airflow (indoor), chemicals concentration in work environment air, etc.) during the period from 1995 to 2021. Rīga Stradiņš University's Institute of Occupational Safety and Environmental Health, Laboratory of Hygiene and Occupational Diseases is accredited (LVS EN ISO/IEC 17025:2017 standard) testing laboratory which mainly focuses on research and prevention of occupational risk factors as well as gives professional measurement services in occupational safety and health to companies.

Origin of the data are measurements provided by the laboratory to clients as commercial service. Laboratory hasn't delegated function of the state to perform inspection measurements, therefore performed measurements are based on the customer's order and free will to carry them out in order to comply with national laws. In some cases (time periods) measurements are performed by the laboratory as a part of European union employer support projects for improving work safety and the working environment, such as ESF project "Labor safety regulatory act practical implementations and improvement of supervision" (No. 7.3.1.0/16/I/001, 2018-2023) or ESF 2007-2013 planning period project "Practical application of labor relations and occupational safety regulations in industries and companies" (No. 1DP/1.3.1.3.2./08/IPIA/NVA/002).

Laboratory measurement data are collected for the research purpose and it relates to the project aim to implement FAIR principles in practice by transforming collected research data in the field of Occupational safety and health (OSH), and to create an openly accessible research data platform.

Dataset consists of laboratory measurements data of different occupational risk factors at the work environment: physical risks (occupational noise, whole body, and hand-arm vibration, indoor lighting, air temperature, relative humidity, airflow) chemical risks (different types of dust, welding aerosols, volatile organic compounds, solvents, metals, acids, hydroxides, aldehydes etc.) or microbiological risks (fungi, total or pathogen microorganisms). Depending on the certain risk factor, measurement method, equipment and measurements results units differs.

In some cases, data are as primary data (indoor lighting, air temperature, relative humidity, airflow), in some cases data are secondary data (recalculated to factor exposure time or to standard environmental conditions), dataset is cleaned from redundant information and anonymized for data protection reasons.

1.1.2 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")?

Research data can be used across multiple domains: researchers in occupational health field, students of the university, occupational safety practitioners, governmental institutions (for example State Labour inspectorate), non-governmental organisations (for example Employer's confederation of Latvia). Different measurements (in groups or combinations) can be analysed in specific cross-sections as economic activities NACE (Nomenclature of Economic Activities) or depending on description of the used equipment in the workplace.

1.2 Data characteristics

1.2.1 Type of data generated/collected

Observation data

1.2.2 Format of data generated/collected

- csv
- sav

1.2.3 Expected volume of the data

12 MB

1.2.4 Are you re-using this dataset?

No

The datasets haven't been published yet, therefore we can't give any reference to previous datasets, however this project is exactly meaning to make these

datasets reusable in future.

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers - DOI)?

Yes

doi

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

DDI (Data Documentation Initiative)

We may add additional metadata regarding specifics of the field, for example, CAS registry numbers to identify different chemical substances

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.1.6 Will you document the dataset?

Yes

- codebook
- readme file
- methodology description

2.2 Data accessibility

2.2.1 Are the data formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

Data will be stored in CSV format which is widely available for most of applications dealing with tabular data. We also plan to store SAV file, therefore making it accessible in SPSS software.

2.2.2 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Data will be accessible with most of the software tools, including MS Excel, SPSS, coding platforms (such as Python, R) and others.

2.2.3 Is it possible to include the relevant software in the dataset (e.g. source code)?

No

2.2.4 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy/ontology to make your data interoperable?

No

Data will be coded with NACE (Nomenclature of Economic Activities) and also CAS registry numbers to enable better accessibility and interoperability of the data to researchers also outside Latvia.

2.3 Data publishing and long-term preservation

2.3.2 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?

Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0

Data is made by efforts of researchers at RSU Institute of Occupational Safety and Environmental Health, therefore it would be appreciated that dataset is

cited also in other studies. We intend that this data can't be used for commercial activities.

2.3.3 What type of access the dataset will have (choose one)?

restricted, request access (access is restricted, but request with collaboration proposal could be submitted to the authors)

Dataset will be shared upon request to other researchers or students who are aiming to use it for research purposes. Dataset may be shared also to state

institutions for policy planning or monitoring purposes. Also, no commercial activity shouldn't be allowed with this data

2.3.4 Will there be an embargo period for access to these data?

No

2.3.5 When data will be made available for re-use?

2023-07-31

Data will be available for re-use for at least 10 years (further researchers will assess necessity for longer preservation). Dataset is important, because it

covers longitudinal study which could be compared also to similar future studies.

2.3.6 Will you provide reference to the dataset in scientific publications and other research outputs?

Yes

2.3.7 Other relevant remarks

We will provide reference to the dataset in scientific publications and other research outputs. Data users should refer to the dataset in case of data use. In

historical scientific publications we will contact the publishers about the

possibilities to provide references.

3.1 Allocation of resources and quality assurance

3.1.1 Which costs will be covered within this project for making data FAIR?

- archiving
- processing

3.1.2 Have you discussed how the costs will be covered?

All costs for processing and archiving data will be covered by the project "Implementing FAIR Principles in the Field of Occupational Safety and Health

(OSH)" (cascading grant under EOSC-Future project funded in Horizon2020

research and innovation framework programme). Only costs for human

resources (remuneration) will be covered within this project, because other (such as licences, workplaces) are covered by the university. Costs for reuse and long-term preservation after the project will be covered by university or other projects.

3.1.3 Which institutions are responsible for handling the data?

Riga Stradiņš University

In this activity only Riga Stradins University will be involved.

3.1.4 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

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guidance and alignment with other activities. Data description and processing

will be done by Svetlana Lakisa and Linda Paegle (researchers at the institute).

3.1.5 Are there data quality assurance processes foreseen?

Yes

Data will be processed and published according to FAIR principles and best practice guidelines. After the project RSU will ensure periodic quality

assessment procedures (in case of necessity, new versions of the datasets will

be published). Quality improvements may be made also when the dataset is re? used by third parties, taking into account their recommendations. Quality assurance will be ensured according to internal policy and procedure

which is developed at the moment.

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall
- Passwords

All data during the project is stored on university data storage which is protected by passwords and centralized and local firewalls. Access is given only

to responsible employees to the respective files.

3.2.2 What provisions are in place for data security?

- Data access
- Data storage
- Data recovery
- Data sharing

Data is accessible only to relevant parties of the project. Data is stored in a safe infrastructure and protected by passwords and firewalls. Data recovery is

possible because backups are made regularly. Data can be shared to other employees.

3.2.3 Where the data will be stored during research?

During research the data will be stored only in the infrastructure described above

3.2.4 Have you ensured that your chosen repository is appropriate for long term preservation and curation?

Yes

Yes, RSU Dataverse is based on Dataverse code which is applicable for long term preservation of the data. University will administer and update the repository on regular basis, as well as ensure data curation.

3.3 Ethical and legal aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

Yes

Data will be fully anonymized to prevent any reference to enterprises and their employees.

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data?

No

3.3.5 Will data collected/generated include sensitive information?

Yes

3.3.6 If yes, what are the methods used to process and access personal data/sensitive information

anonymising data

Data will be fully anonymized ensuring confidentiality of enterprises involved in the measurement process.

Title: [Working conditions and risks in Latvia - focus group interviews](#)

Template: [RSU DMP Template](#)

The aim of the research is to clarify the current situation in the field of occupational safety and health in Latvia, to analyze the dynamics of the obtained data and to develop proposals for improving the practical implementation of the legal framework. The study is necessary in order to implement a high quality and targeted policy in the field of labor relations and occupational safety and health, to monitor and understand the current situation and to identify the causes of the existing problems.

Dataset Description

1.1 Purpose of data

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The study "Working conditions and risks in Latvia 2012-2013" was created with the financial support of the European Social Fund of the European Union and the Latvian state of the Latvian Employers' Confederation project "Practical application of labor relations and occupational safety regulatory acts in industries and companies" (No. 1DP/1.3. 1.3.2./08/IPIA/NVA/002).

The study "Working conditions and risks in Latvia, 2019-2021" was carried out on the order of the State Labor Inspectorate within the framework of the ESF project "Improving the practical implementation and monitoring of occupational safety regulations" (project identification No. 7.3.1.0/16/I/001).

Focus group discussions with employers or their representatives and occupational safety and health experts (with higher education) on various topics related to the work environment. The discussion includes the following topics:

- workplace safety and laws,

- for a long and productive working life,
- remote work (in 2022),
- COVID -19 (in 2022),
- government control and oversight in the area of occupational safety,
- information on occupational safety issues,
- causes of accidents, measures to reduce the number of accidents and occupational diseases,
- possibilities of further development of the system of occupational safety services.

1.1.2 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")?

To occupational health and safety researchers and practitioners, students, for the State Labor Inspectorate, trade unions and other interested parties.

1.2 Data characteristics

1.2.1 Type of data generated/collected

Textual data

1.2.2 Format of data generated/collected

- txt
- pdf

1.2.3 Expected volume of the data

- a. 484 KB
- b. 1253 KB

1.2.4 Are you re-using this dataset?

No

The datasets haven't been published yet, therefore we can't give any reference to previous datasets, however this project is exactly meaning to make these datasets reusable in future.

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers - DOI)?

Yes

doi

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

DDI (Data Documentation Initiative)

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.1.6 Will you document the dataset?

Yes

- readme file
- questionnaire
- methodology description

2.2 Data accessibility

2.2.1 Are the data formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

Data will be stored in TXT and PDF formats which are appropriate for many software tools for textual data.

2.2.2 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Data will be accessible with most of the software tools, including MS Word, NVIVO etc.

2.2.3 Is it possible to include the relevant software in the dataset (e.g. source code)?

No

2.2.4 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy/ontology to make your data interoperable?

No

2.3 Data publishing and long-term preservation

2.3.2 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

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restricted, request access (access is restricted, but request with collaboration proposal could be submitted to the authors)

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No

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Data will be available for re-use for at least 10 years (further researchers will assess necessity for longer preservation).

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Yes

2.3.7 Other relevant remarks

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historical scientific publications we will contact the publishers about the possibilities to provide references.

3.1 Allocation of resources and quality assurance

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- archiving
- processing

3.1.2 Have you discussed how the costs will be covered?

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Yes

Data will be processed and published according to FAIR principles and best practice guidelines. After the project RSU will ensure periodic quality assessment procedures (in case of necessity, new versions of the datasets will

be published). Quality improvements may be made also when the dataset is re-used by third parties, taking into account their recommendations. Quality assurance will be ensured according to internal policy and procedure which is developed at the moment.

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

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- Passwords

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Data is accessible only to relevant parties of the project. Data is stored in a safe infrastructure and protected by passwords and firewalls. Data recovery is possible because backups are made regularly. Data can be shared to other employees.

3.2.3 Where the data will be stored during research?

Data will be stored only in the infrastructure described above during research.

3.2.4 Have you ensured that your chosen repository is appropriate for long term preservation and curation?

Yes

Yes, RSU Dataverse is based on Dataverse code which is applicable for long-term preservation of the data. University will administer and update the repository on regular basis, as well as ensure data curation.

3.3 Ethical and legal aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

Data has been anonymized prior to this project, so there are no ethical or legal issues.

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data (if applicable)?

Yes

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data?

Yes

3.3.5 Will data collected/generated include sensitive information?

Yes

3.3.6 If yes, what are the methods used to process and access personal data/sensitive information

anonymising data

Data will be anonymized, as well as information which could be sensitive will be excluded from the transcripts. It will be evaluated by project team members according to best practice guidelines provided by CESSDA.

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